

TAILORING OF A LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE UNDER STRUCTURAL CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

The tailoring effects of a laminated composite plate under the active vibration control with the piezoelectric sensors/actuators are investigated. The stiffness and damping of a composite structure can be altered by the tailoring. In structural control, the tailoring of a composite structure and the design of numbers and locations of the piezoelectric sensors/actuators can reduce the cancel-out of signal by the integrated effect. The integrated effect of a piezoelectric sensor/actuator and the bending-torsional coupling of a composite structure are the important factors in the vibrational control system design.

Keywords : Laminated Plate, Tailoring, Piezoelectric Sensor/Actuator, Structural Control

1. INTRODUCTION

With the requirements of accuracy in positioning and low amplitude vibrations, it is necessary for a space structure to be strong and capable of high precision and efficiency while the large space structures are required to be lightweight. In many cases, saving weight results in increased flexibility. This may cause structural instability, such as fracture or undesired large amplitude vibration. Besides, these problems lead to a drastic reduction in accuracy and precision of operation. Thus, it is highly desirable to control excessive vibration and to stabilize the structure during operation^[1-2]. The control can be exerted by using either active or passive control methods or both. The active control method counteracts the motion of a structure by the external control forces. The passive control method modifies the structural properties without using any external energy supply^[3].

An active control system, using distributed piezoelectric sensors and actuators, has proven to be effective in controlling the vibration of distributed elastic systems. Since structures are distributed parameter systems having an infinite set of vibration modes, distributed measurement and control is required. Distributed sensors/actuators (S/A's), which can detect and generate a number of vibration modes simultaneously and reduce the control spillover, are desirable to remedy the drawbacks of point S/A's. The use of PZT ceramics and PVDF thin film as a distributed active damper for beam vibration has been studied^[4-11].

As a passive control method, the tailoring of a composite structure can be used. Recent advances in design and manufacturing technologies have greatly enhanced the use of advanced fiber-reinforced composite materials for aircraft and aerospace structural applications. In addition to their high stiffness-to-weight ratio and strength-to-weight ratio, it is possible to control their structural properties by tailoring, which modifies the structural properties of the system without addition of materials or mechanisms^[12-13]. In structural vibration control, the alteration of vibration modes with the change of stiffness and damping can affect performance. Thus, the integration of

composite structural design with the intelligent system concept could potentially enhance the performance of the structural vibration control.

In this paper, the effects of the tailoring of a laminated composite plate under the active vibration control are investigated. The active vibration control by the piezoelectric S/A's and the passive vibration control by the tailoring are performed simultaneously. The stiffness and damping of a composite structure can be altered by the tailoring. The piezoelectric S/A's, which are known to be distributed, are not perfectly distributed but integrated due to the effect of electrode. The integrated effect of a piezoelectric S/A and the bending-torsional coupling of a composite structure are the important factors in vibration control system design. In structural control, the tailoring of a composite structure and the design of numbers and locations of the piezoelectric sensors/actuators can reduce the cancel-out of signal by the integrated effect. For the various S/A models, the damping ratios and the settling times are calculated with the change of the layer angles.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The governing equations of a laminated plate with piezoelectric S/A in Figure 1 are derived in the reference [11] using the finite element method, and can be summarized briefly as follows:

The discretized equation of motion for a laminated composite plate with piezoelectric control force is

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{r}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{F}^E + \mathbf{F}^C \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{K} the stiffness matrix, \mathbf{F}^E the external force vector, \mathbf{F}^C the control force vector, and \mathbf{r} the nodal displacement vector. The control force by the j -th piezoelectric actuator is written as a function of input voltage:

$$\mathbf{F}_j^C = \mathbf{\Xi}_j V_j^A \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{\Xi}_j$ is the actuating coefficient matrix and V_j^A is the actuator voltage for the j -th actuator. A piezoelectric strain-rate sensor can detect the velocity of a structure where it is attached. The sensor voltage V_j^S from the j -th sensor can be written:

$$V_j^S = G_j^C \mathbf{\Theta}_j \dot{\mathbf{r}} \quad (3)$$

where G_j^C is the gain of current transformer, and $\mathbf{\Theta}_j$ the sensing coefficient matrix for the j -th sensor. The sensor voltage is fed back to an actuator by the constant gain feedback control law which is:

$$V_j^A = G_j V_j^S \quad (4)$$

where G_j is the feedback gain of the j -th S/A.

3. MODAL STATE SPACE ANALYSIS

3.1. State Space Equation of Motion with Feedback Control Law

Using the orthogonality of the eigenvectors with respect to the mass matrix and the stiffness matrix, modal coordinates are introduced as follows,

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\eta} \quad (5)$$

Figure1. Diagram for vibration control of a plate with piezoelectric S/A

where Φ is the modal matrix. When the modal state variable $\mathbf{x} = \text{col} \{ \boldsymbol{\eta} \ \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} \}$ is introduced, the modal state space equations of motion with control forces are as follows,

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -[\omega^2] & -\bar{\mathbf{C}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \Phi^T \boldsymbol{\Xi}_1 & \Phi^T \boldsymbol{\Xi}_2 & \dots & \Phi^T \boldsymbol{\Xi}_{NSA} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \{ V_1^A \ V_2^A \ \dots \ V_{NSA}^A \}^T$$

and (NSA) is the number of S/A. The modal structural damping matrix $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ is derived from the definition of specific damping capacity in Adams et al.^[14]. The sensor equation in modal state space is

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mathbf{y} = \{ V_1^S \ V_2^S \ \dots \ V_{NSA}^S \}^T, \quad \mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ (\Theta_1 \Phi)^T & (\Theta_2 \Phi)^T & \dots & (\Theta_{NSA} \Phi)^T \end{bmatrix}$$

If negative velocity feedback control is applied, the sensor voltage is multiplied by the feedback gain and fed to the actuator. The linear feedback control law is

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x} \quad (8)$$

where the gain matrix \mathbf{G} is

$$\mathbf{G} = \text{diag} \{ G_1 G_1^C \ G_2 G_2^C \ \dots \ G_{NSA} G_{NSA}^C \} \quad (9)$$

3.2. Complex Eigen-Solution Method

When the feedback control law in Equation 8 is inserted into Equation 7, the modal state space equations of motion are as follows,

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{x} \quad (10)$$

This can be analyzed as a complex eigenvalue problem,

$$[\lambda \mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C})] \{ \phi \} = 0 \quad (11)$$

and the complex eigenvalue is

$$\lambda = \sigma + i \omega_d \quad (12)$$

Two measures of dynamic stability are the real part of the complex eigenvalue and the damping ratio. The imaginary part is 2π times the damped frequency and the damping ratio is defined to be the negative of the normalized real part of the complex eigenvalue.

$$f_d = \frac{\omega_d}{2\pi} \quad \zeta = \frac{-\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \omega_d^2}} \quad (13)$$

where f_d is the damped frequency and ζ the damping ratio. The time required for the displacement to be one half of the initial displacement, $T_{1/2}$, is derived from the logarithmic decrement.

$$T_{1/2} = n T = \frac{n}{f} = \frac{\ln 2}{2\pi \zeta f} \quad (14)$$

In Equation 14, $T_{1/2}$ contains the damped frequency and damping ratio for the specific mode, so $T_{1/2}$ can be a good measure of damping capacity, considering the effects of stiffness and damping.

3.3. Effects of Tailoring

The matrices **A**, **B**, **G**, **C**, consisting the system equations in Equation 10 are dependent on the structural and control variables. The response of system is controlled by modifying these variables.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &= \mathbf{A}(\omega, \phi), & \mathbf{B} &= \mathbf{B}(\Xi, \Phi), \\ \mathbf{C} &= \mathbf{C}(\Theta, \Phi), & \mathbf{G} &= \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^C) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where the natural frequencies ω , the modal damping matrix ϕ , and the modal matrix Φ are the functions of layer angles q . Therefore the stiffness and damping properties and the mode shapes of a laminated plate can be modified by the tailoring. Ξ and Θ are dependent on the number, size and locations of S/A's. **G** is dependent on the feedback gains of each S/A pairs.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A plate composed of laminated composites whose stacking sequence is $[\theta_1 / \theta_2 / 0^\circ / 90^\circ]_s$ with piezoelectric S/A pairs shown in Figure 2 is considered. One side of the plate is fixed and the other sides are free. The sensors are attached over the whole upper surface and the actuators over the lower surface. The S/A's can be divided arbitrarily, but must be collocated. The material properties of the Graphite/Epoxy lamina (Hercules AS1/3501-6) and PZT-5A (Clevite Corp.) are shown in Table 1. Thirty six elements (6×6) are used to model the plate and the S/A pair can be attached for each element. Six modes are used in modal space analysis.

Figure 2. Laminated plate with piezoelectric S/A

Table 1. Material Properties

	Graphitic/Epoxy Lamina		PZT-5A
E_1	$98. \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$	s_{11}	$16.4 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$
E_2	$7.9 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$	s_{12}	$-5.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$
G_{12}	$5.6 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$	s_{33}	$18.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$
t	0.125 mm	s_{55}	$47.5 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$
ν_{12}	0.28	d_{31}	$-171 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/N}$
ρ	1520 kg/m^3	d_{33}	$374 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/N}$
ϕ_1	0.0045	d_{15}	$584 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/N}$
ϕ_2	0.0420	ϵ_{11}	$.153 \times 10^{-7} \text{ F/m}$
ϕ_{12}	0.0706	ϵ_{33}	$.150 \times 10^{-7} \text{ F/m}$
		l	0.1 mm

4.1. Tailoring of a Laminated Composite Plate without Active Control

To investigate the tailoring effect of a laminated plate, the bending stiffness D_{11} , the bending-torsional coupling D_{12} , and the torsional stiffness D_{66} are calculated as shown in Figure 3, varying the layer angle θ from 0° to 90° with $\theta_1 = -\theta_2$ or $\theta_1 = \theta_2$. The bending stiffness is maximum when

$\theta=0^\circ$, and minimum when $\theta=90^\circ$. The torsional stiffness is maximum when $\theta=45^\circ$ and minimum when $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=90^\circ$. The bending-torsional coupling is maximum when $\theta=30^\circ$ and 0 when $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=90^\circ$. Later we will call the plate of $\theta_1=-\theta_2$ as a balanced plate and that of $\theta_1=\theta_2$ as an unbalanced plate. The damped frequency and the damping ratio without the active control by the piezoelectric S/A's are obtained. The order of the vibration modes are changed as the layer angles change. In addition, the vibration mode shapes are slightly changed since the bending-torsional coupling is changed. Due to the characteristics of the fiber and the polymer matrix, the frequencies and damping ratios can be controlled by tailoring. Generally the frequencies and damping ratio are inversely proportional to each other as in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Bending stiffness Figure 4. Damped frequencies and damping ratios without control

4.2. Tailoring of a Laminated Composite Plate with Active Control

The damped frequency and the damping ratio with the active control by the piezoelectric S/A's are obtained. To investigate the effect of the division of S/A pairs, model A with one S/A pair, model B with 36 S/A pairs and model C with two S/A pairs over the whole surface are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Models with various sensors/actuators

The simulations are performed with the varying layer angles and $GG^C = 10000$. The damping ratios of the balanced plate for the first bending and torsional modes are shown in Figure 6. For the first bending mode, all models show increased damping ratios for any layer angle, with the maximum improvement at $\theta=90^\circ$. The settling times show much reduction for any layer angle θ . In case of the first torsional mode, for model B the damping ratios increase by the same amount regardless of the layer angle. However for model A, the damping ratio is invariant with respect to the feedback gains for the first torsional mode. This is due to the property that a distributed piezoelectric sensor cannot detect the skew-symmetric deformation. One way of overcoming this drawback in model A is to use a composite plate with skewed layer angles of $\theta=45^\circ$, which gives not skew-symmetric torsional modes and good damping capacities for those modes. Model B with 36 S/A pairs is best at $\theta=0^\circ$ and 90° , since it shows good damping for the first torsional mode. Since each S/A pair requires one feedback control loop, the increase in the number of the S/A pairs means that more control loops are required. Therefore, the design with the minimum number of S/A pairs is preferable. The S/A system with one pair shows good damping capacities, except for its inability to control a symmetric deformation. To overcome this drawback, model C with two S/A pairs is suggested. The results for model C in Figure 6 show similar damping ratios to model A, however the drawbacks of model A are overcome at $\theta=0^\circ$ and 90° . Thus, model C is a mixture of models A and B, making use of the advantage of each system. The damping ratios of the

unbalanced plate for the first bending and torsional modes are shown in Figure 7. The results are the same with those in Figure 6. However the damping ratios are more improved since the bending-torsional coupling is larger than those of the balanced plate.

Figure 6. Damping ratios and settling times of a balanced plate (○ : no control, ● : model A, □ : model B, ■ : model C)

Figure 7. Damping ratios and settling times of an unbalanced plate (○ : no control, ● : model A, □ : model B, ■ : model C)

5. CONCLUSIONS

The mode shapes of a laminated plate have changed slightly by the tailoring. The observation and control of the torsional modes in structural vibration are possible by making use of the bending-torsional coupling.

In designing active control systems, the number and the sizes of the S/A pairs must be considered as design variables while the total area of the S/A system is the same. By proper design of distributed S/A's, an efficient active control system can be designed for a specified layer angle. Since the tailoring and the S/A design affect each other, they should be considered simultaneously in designing efficient controlled structures.

References

1. Rogers, C.A., *Intelligent Material Systems and Structures, U.S.-Japan Workshop on Smart/ Intelligent Materials and Systems*, Technomic Publishing Co., 1990, pp.11-33.
2. Wada, B.K., Fanson, J.L., and Crawley, E.F., *Adaptive Structures*, edited by B.K. Wada, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 1989, pp.1-8.
3. Leipholz, H.H.E. and Abdel-Rohman, M., *Control of Structures*, Martinus Nijhoff Pub., The Netherlands, 1986.
4. Bailey, T. and Hubbard, J.E., Jr., *Distributed Piezoelectric Polymer Active Vibration Control of a Cantilever Beam*, *Journal of Guidance and Control*, Vol.8, No.5, 1985, pp.606 - 610.
5. Crawley, E.F. and de Luis, J., *Use of Piezoelectric Actuators as Elements of Intelligent Structures*, *AIAA Journal*, Vol.25, No.10, 1987, pp. 1373-1385.
6. Crawley, E.F. and Lazarus, K.B., *Induced Strain Actuation of Isotropic and Anisotropic Plates*, *AIAA Journal*, Vol.29, 1991, pp. 944-951.
7. Wang, B.T. and Rogers, C.A., *Laminate Plate Theory for Spatially Distributed Induced Strain Actuators*, *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.25, 1991, pp. 433-452
8. Lee, C.-K., *Piezoelectric Laminates for Torsional and Bending Control : Theory and Experiments*, Ph.D. dissertation, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, 1987.
9. Tzou, H.S. and Tseng, C.-I., *Distributed Vibration Control and Identification of Coupled Elastic / Piezoelectric Systems : Finite Element Formulation and Application*, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, Vol.5, No.3, 1991, pp.215-231.
10. Ha, S.K., Keilers, C. and Chang, F.K., *Finite Element Analysis of Composite Structures Containing Distributed Piezoelectric Sensors and Actuators*, *AIAA Journal*, Vol.30, No.3, 1992, pp. 772-780.
11. Hwang, W.-S. and Park, H.C., *Finite Element Modeling of Piezoelectric Sensor/Actuator*, *AIAA Journal*, (in press).
12. Schmit, L.A. and Farshi, B., *Optimum Laminate Design for Strength and Stiffness*, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol.7, 1973, pp.519 - 536.
13. Haftka, R.T., Gurdal, G. and Kamat, M.P., *Elements of Structural Optimization*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, The Netherlands, 1990.
14. Lin, D.X., Ni, R.G. and Adams, R.D., *Prediction and Measurement of the Vibrational Damping Parameters of Carbon and Glass Fiber-Reinforced Plastic Plates*, *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.18, 1984, pp. 132-152.